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Rahim Thawer - Queer Mental Health Media Archive

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Abstract

Addresses therapist anxiety when working with parents and caregivers of queer and trans youth, exploring fears of unintentional harm, family resistance, and systemic limitations. Offers strategies to manage clinical reactivity, establish productive alliances with families, and navigate value differences while prioritizing youth safety. Highlights psychoeducation, assertive communication, and professional self-regulation.

Keywords

LGBTQ+, family, clinical practice

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